

**AVALIAÇÃO DAS EMISSÕES E DO CONSUMO DE COMBUSTÍVEL DE
CAMINHÕES PESADOS OPERANDO COM MISTURAS DE BIODIESEL NO
BRASIL**

***ASSESSMENT OF EMISSIONS AND FUEL CONSUMPTION OF HEAVY-DUTY
TRUCKS OPERATING WITH BIODIESEL BLENDS IN BRAZIL***

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Resumo

Este estudo avalia os efeitos das misturas de biodiesel sobre as emissões de gases de escape e o consumo de combustível em caminhões pesados representativos de duas gerações tecnológicas da frota brasileira. Os veículos testados atendem às normas de emissões PROCONVE P5 e P7 e representam uma parcela significativa da frota nacional. Os ensaios experimentais foram realizados em dinamômetro de chassi seguindo a metodologia dos ciclos de condução da ABNT NBR 15634. Os resultados mostraram que o veículo mais moderno, padrão P7, apresentou emissões de NO_x estáveis para diferentes misturas de biodiesel devido à presença de sistemas avançados de gerenciamento eletrônico e pós-tratamento de gases. Em contraste, o veículo mais antigo, padrão P5, apresentou maior sensibilidade à concentração de biodiesel, com aumento nas emissões de NO_x e no consumo de combustível. Ambos os veículos apresentaram aumento do consumo específico de combustível com a elevação do teor de biodiesel, enquanto as emissões de hidrocarbonetos permaneceram desprezíveis. As emissões de CO₂ mostraram-se mais estáveis no veículo mais moderno. Os resultados confirmam a conformidade com a atual legislação brasileira de emissões, ao mesmo tempo em que evidenciam a maior sensibilidade das tecnologias diesel mais antigas ao aumento da concentração de biodiesel. O estudo também destaca a importância de avaliar os impactos operacionais e ambientais associados ao aumento do teor de biodiesel em frotas envelhecidas.

Palavras-Chave: Misturas de biodiesel. Caminhões pesados. Emissões de escapamento.

Abstract

This study evaluates the effects of biodiesel blends on exhaust emissions and fuel consumption in heavy-duty trucks representative of two technological generations of the Brazilian fleet. The tested vehicles comply with PROCONVE P5 and P7 emission standards and represent a significant portion of the national fleet. Experimental tests were conducted on a chassis dynamometer following the ABNT NBR 15634 driving cycle methodology. Results showed that the newer P7 vehicle exhibited stable NO_x emissions across different biodiesel blends due to the presence of advanced electronic management and aftertreatment systems. In contrast, the

older P5 vehicle presented higher sensitivity to biodiesel concentration, with increased NO_x emissions and fuel consumption. Both vehicles showed higher specific fuel consumption as biodiesel content increased, while hydrocarbon emissions remained negligible. CO₂ emissions were more stable in the newer vehicle. The results confirm compliance with current Brazilian emission regulations while highlighting the greater sensitivity of older heavy-duty technologies to biodiesel blending. The study also indicates the importance of evaluating operational and environmental impacts associated with increasing biodiesel content in aging fleets.

Keywords: Biodiesel blends. Heavy-duty trucks. Exhaust emissions.

1. Introduction

Heavy-duty diesel vehicles are major contributors to atmospheric pollutant emissions due to their high load operation, extended service life and elevated annual mileage. In Brazil, the expansion of road transportation and the aging profile of the diesel fleet have intensified concerns regarding fuel consumption, greenhouse gas emissions and urban air quality (DE CARVALHO, 2016; PEREIRA *et al.*, 2021). Among the regulated pollutants associated with diesel combustion, nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and particulate matter (PM) are particularly relevant because of their environmental and public health impacts.

To reduce vehicular emissions, Brazil progressively implemented stricter emission regulations through the Program for the Control of Air Pollution from Motor Vehicles (PROCONVE), established by CONAMA Resolution No. 18/1986. Successive PROCONVE phases promoted technological advances in combustion control, electronic engine management and exhaust aftertreatment systems. Vehicles compliant with PROCONVE P7 standards are generally equipped with advanced technologies such as Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR), Diesel Particulate Filters (DPF) and Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR), whereas older PROCONVE P5 vehicles operate with less sophisticated emission control strategies (BRASIL, 2002; BRASIL, 2008; IBAMA, 2022).

In parallel with emission regulations, Brazil has expanded the mandatory incorporation of biodiesel into commercial diesel fuel as part of its renewable energy and decarbonization strategy. According to the National Energy Balance, biodiesel participation in the Brazilian energy matrix has increased significantly in recent years, reaching mandatory blends up to B15 (EPE, 2025; MME, 2025). Biodiesel presents advantages such as renewability, oxygenated composition and potential reduction of lifecycle greenhouse gas emissions. However, differences in physicochemical properties between biodiesel and fossil diesel may affect combustion characteristics, pollutant formation and fuel consumption.

Previous studies have shown that biodiesel blends generally reduce carbon monoxide (CO), hydrocarbon (HC) and particulate emissions, while their influence on NO_x emissions and fuel consumption depends on engine technology, operating conditions and after treatment efficiency (ATABANI *et al.*, 2012; AZAD *et al.*, 2023; ALTARAZI *et al.*, 2022). In older diesel technologies, higher biodiesel concentrations may increase NO_x emissions due to changes in combustion temperature and ignition characteristics, whereas modern vehicles equipped with SCR systems tend to exhibit greater emission stability (ZARE *et al.*, 2021).

The effects of biodiesel blending are particularly relevant in Brazil because a substantial portion of the heavy-duty fleet still consists of older vehicles operating under previous PROCONVE phases. According to the Sindipeças fleet report, the coexistence of vehicles with different technological standards results in heterogeneous responses regarding emissions and fuel consumption under alternative fuel operation (SINDIPEÇAS, 2023).

Accurate assessment of emissions and fuel consumption under transient operation requires experimental procedures capable of reproducing real driving conditions. Chassis dynamometer tests using standardized driving cycles allow the integrated evaluation of engine performance, transmission behavior and exhaust aftertreatment efficiency. In Brazil, ABNT NBR 15634 establishes procedures for measuring gaseous pollutants and fuel consumption in heavy-duty diesel vehicles under controlled laboratory conditions. According to Quirama *et al.* (2020), transient driving cycles are essential for reproducing realistic vehicle operating conditions and obtaining representative emission measurements.

Therefore, this study evaluates the effects of biodiesel blends on exhaust emissions and fuel consumption in two heavy-duty trucks representative of different technological generations of the Brazilian fleet, compliant with PROCONVE P5 and P7 standards. Experimental tests were conducted on a chassis dynamometer following the ABNT NBR 15634 methodology. The objective is to quantify the influence of biodiesel concentration on NO_x, CO, HC, CO₂ emissions and specific fuel consumption, as well as to assess the sensitivity of older and newer diesel technologies to biodiesel operation.

2. Methodology

Experimental tests were conducted to evaluate the effects of biodiesel blends on exhaust emissions and fuel consumption in heavy-duty diesel vehicles representative of different technological generations of the Brazilian fleet. The experimental procedure included vehicle instrumentation, chassis dynamometer testing, transient driving cycle operation and exhaust gas analysis under controlled laboratory conditions.

Two heavy-duty trucks compliant with different emission standards were evaluated. The first vehicle represented newer diesel technology meeting P7 requirements and equipped with Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR), Diesel Particulate Filter (DPF) and Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR) systems. The second vehicle represented older fleet technology certified under the P5 phase, operating with less advanced emission control strategies.

Tests were performed on a Dynamite chassis dynamometer following the procedures established by ABNT NBR 15634 for heavy-duty diesel vehicles. The adopted transient driving cycle reproduced representative operating conditions including acceleration, deceleration, idle and load variation events. Exhaust emissions and fuel consumption were continuously monitored throughout the experimental campaign.

The evaluated fuel blends consisted of commercial diesel containing different biodiesel concentrations. Emission measurements included nitrogen oxides (NO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), hydrocarbons (HC) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). Specific fuel consumption and operational parameters were also determined to assess the influence of biodiesel concentration on vehicle performance and emission behavior.

2.1 Performance Parameters

Engine performance was evaluated using effective power, indicated mean effective pressure (IMEP), specific fuel consumption and overall efficiency parameters. These variables were adopted to compare vehicle behavior under different biodiesel blending conditions.

The compression ratio (ϵ) was determined according to Eq. (1):

$$\epsilon = \frac{V_d + V_c}{V_c} \quad (1)$$

where: $V_d \rightarrow$ Displacement volume; $V_c \rightarrow$ Combustion chamber volume.

Effective power (\dot{W}_e), was calculated from engine rotational speed and torque according to Heywood (2018):

$$\dot{W}_e = 2\pi N\tau \quad (2)$$

where (N) is the engine rotational speed and (τ) is the engine torque.

According to Vago (2022), an engine's torque is a distinctive characteristic influenced by variations in engine sizes and configurations. To mitigate the impact of this specificity, the concept of indicated mean effective pressure (IMEP) is used. This represents the pressure that should be applied inside the cylinder, in a complete cycle, to produce the same work as during the engine's standard operation. The indicated mean effective pressure (IMEP) was determined by:

$$IMEP = \frac{\oint P_c \times dV_a}{V_t} \quad (3)$$

where: P_c is the in-cylinder pressure; dV_a is the cylinder volume variation and V_t is the total displacement volume.

The thermal power released during combustion was estimated by:

$$\dot{Q} = \dot{m}_f \times LHV \quad (4)$$

where (\dot{m}_f) is the fuel mass flow rate and (LHV) is the lower heating value of the fuel.

The stoichiometric air-fuel ratio was calculated according to:

$$(A/F)_{sc} = \frac{\dot{m}_{air}}{\dot{m}_f} \quad (5)$$

where \dot{m}_{air} is the air mass flow rate.

The excess air ratio (λ) was determined from the ratio between actual and stoichiometric air-fuel ratios:

$$\lambda = \frac{(A/F)_a}{(A/F)_{sc}} \quad (6)$$

Specific fuel consumption was determined by:

$$C_e = \frac{\dot{m}_f}{P_e} \quad (7)$$

where (P_e) is the effective engine power.

Overall engine efficiency was estimated according to:

$$\eta_e = \frac{1}{bsfc \times LHV} \quad (8)$$

where (bsfc) is the brake specific fuel consumption.

2.2 Vehicle Instrumentation and Experimental Setup

The vehicles were secured to the chassis dynamometer using four ratchet straps with “J” hooks attached to anchoring points fixed to the laboratory floor. A crossed fixation arrangement was adopted to improve vehicle stability during transient operation.

Fuel consumption measurements were performed using a Toledo 9094C/5 electronic scale with Inmetro Class III certification and resolution of ± 2 g. The fuel supply system was connected to an auxiliary tank positioned on the scale, allowing continuous gravimetric monitoring of fuel mass variation during the driving cycle.

Vehicle tests were conducted on a Dynamite chassis dynamometer equipped with a 12-inch roller and Eddy Current Brake system, with a maximum power capacity of 700 hp. The dynamometer acquisition system continuously monitored vehicle speed, torque and operating conditions throughout the tests. The main specifications of the experimental equipment are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. PC - MULTIGÁS Technical Specifications

Technical Data	PC - MULTIGÁS
Power Supply:	12VDC or 110/220VAC - 60Hz
CO	0 - 15% (Carbon Monoxide)
CO ₂	0 - 20% (Carbon Dioxide)
HC	0 - 20000ppm (Hydrocarbons referenced to Hexane)
O ₂	0 - 25% (Oxygen)
NO _x	0 - 5000ppm (Nitric Oxide)
Lambda	0 - 9.99
AFR	0 - 99.99 Air Fuel Ratio
Serial Interface	RS 232C

Source: NAPRO (2013).

Exhaust gas emissions were measured using a NAPRO PC-MULTIGÁS analyzer equipped with non-dispersive infrared (NDIR) sensors for CO, CO₂ and HC measurements and electrochemical sensors for O₂ and NO_x analysis. The analyzer also included an integrated gas dehumidification system to improve measurement stability during transient operation.

Two heavy-duty trucks representative of different technological generations of the Brazilian fleet were evaluated. The first vehicle was a 2022 Mercedes-Benz Accelo 815 compliant with PROCONVE P7 standards and equipped with EGR, DPF and SCR aftertreatment systems using ARLA-32 injection. The second vehicle was a 2010 Ford Cargo 815 compliant with PROCONVE P5 standards and equipped with EGR and DPF systems. The main technical specifications of the evaluated vehicles are presented in Table 2.

Data acquisition from the dynamometer and exhaust gas analyzer was performed continuously using dedicated acquisition software throughout the experimental campaign. For the tests, two trucks were used with different engine regulations: a 2022 Mercedes Accelo 815 governed by Proconve P7, utilizing the SCR post-treatment system with the addition of Arla-32, an exhaust gas recirculation valve (EGR), and a diesel particulate filter (DPF), and a 2010 Ford Cargo 815 governed by Proconve P5, with EGR and DPF. The technical specifications are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Technical Specifications of the Trucks

Technical Specifications	Mercedes Accelo 815 2022	Ford Cargo 815 2010
Engine	MB OM 924 LA	Cummins Interact
Bore x Stroke	106mm x136mm	102mm x 120mm
Power	156hp@2200rpm	150hp@2500rpm
Torque	580Nm@1200rpm	550Nm@1500rpm
Post-treatment	EGR, DPF, SCR	EGR, DPF

Source: Mercedes-Benz (2020), Ford (2010).

2.3 Driving Cycle and Fuel Blend Preparation

Experimental tests were conducted according to the procedures established by ABNT NBR 15634 for heavy-duty diesel vehicles under transient operating conditions. The adopted driving cycle reproduced representative urban and highway operation, including acceleration, deceleration, idle and variable load conditions. The complete cycle duration was 1800 s and was performed on the chassis dynamometer under controlled laboratory conditions.

Vehicle speed and operating conditions were continuously monitored throughout the tests using the dynamometer acquisition system. The adopted driving cycle profile is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Speed for Conducting the Driving Cycle

Time (s)	Gear Order	Speed (km/h)
0 - 60	2	20
60 - 150	3	40
150 - 180	Neutral	0
180 - 210	2	20
210 - 240	Neutral	0
240 - 600	3	40
600 - 720	Neutral	0
720 - 900	3	40
900 - 1200	4	60
1200 - 1320	Neutral	0
1320 - 1800	4 and 5	80

Source: Authors (2026).

The evaluated fuels consisted of commercial diesel containing different biodiesel concentrations by volume. The tested blends included B0, B7, B15, B20 and B70 fuels, representative of current and projected biodiesel incorporation levels in the Brazilian diesel market. The biodiesel concentration was determined according to Eq. (9):

$$C_{(\%)} = \frac{V_b}{V_d + V_b} \quad (9)$$

where (V_b) is the biodiesel volume and (V_d) is the diesel volume.

Before each experimental test, the fuel system was stabilized to minimize residual fuel contamination between consecutive biodiesel blends. Fuel mass variation was continuously monitored during the complete driving cycle to determine fuel consumption and specific fuel consumption parameters.

Exhaust gas concentrations of NO_x, CO, HC and CO₂ were continuously measured during the experimental campaign. Emission measurements were integrated over the complete driving cycle according to ABNT NBR 15634 procedures.

The actual engine rotational speed during the cycle was determined according to Eq. (10):

$$n_{actual} = \frac{\%n \times (n_{ref} - n_{\varepsilon})}{100} + n_{\varepsilon} \quad (10)$$

where (%n) is the normalized engine speed, (n_{ref}) is the reference engine speed and (n_{ε}) is the idle speed.

The actual engine torque was calculated according to Eq. (11):

$$Torque_{real} = \frac{\%torque \times torque_{max}}{100} \quad (11)$$

where (%torque) is the normalized torque value and ($torque_{max}$) is the maximum engine torque.

3. Results and Discussion

The combustion of diesel and biodiesel generates gaseous emissions that may affect air quality and human health. In this section, the emissions of oxygen (O₂), carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and carbon dioxide (CO₂), resulting from the combustion of diesel fuel containing different biodiesel concentrations are analyzed for two heavy-duty trucks compliant with different emission standards.

According to the procedures established by ABNT NBR 15634, described in the previous section, comparative tests were conducted using the ETC and ESC driving cycles for both evaluated vehicles. Although the trucks belonged to the same engine category, they were equipped with different exhaust aftertreatment technologies. In general, the emission analysis was based on the average values directly obtained from the exhaust gas analyzer measurements in accordance with the standard procedures.

The results provided by the NAPRO gas analyzer are expressed in parts per million by volume (ppm vol.). However, according to ABNT NBR 15634, the emission results must be presented in terms of specific mass emissions. Therefore, the measured volumetric concentrations were converted into specific emissions considering the density of each pollutant component, as required by the standard.

The conversion procedure can be mathematically expressed by Eq. (12):

$$GAS_x = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} (m_{GASi} \times W_{Fi})}{\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} (P(n)_i \times W_{Fi})} \quad (12)$$

where (m_{GAS_i}) is the mass of the analyzed gas component, $(P(n)_i)$ is the useful engine power according to ABNT NBR 15634, and (W_{Fi}) is the weighting factor associated with each operating mode.

Table 4 presents the density values adopted for each analyzed emission component according to ABNT NBR 15634. In the present study, these values were used to correct the raw exhaust gas measurements obtained during the experimental tests.

Table 4 Density values of emission components

Exhaust Gas	NO _x	CO	HC	CO ₂
Raw	0.001587	0.000966	0.000479	0.001518
Diluted	0.001588	0.000967	0.000480	0.001519

Source: NBR 15634.

3.1 Performance Comparison

The evaluation of vehicle performance under different biodiesel blending conditions revealed a direct relationship between fuel composition, engine operating behavior and pollutant emissions. The analysis allowed the identification of important effects associated with the use of higher biodiesel concentrations in heavy-duty diesel vehicles with different technological standards.

According to the procedures established by ABNT NBR 15634, the tests were conducted using progressive load and engine speed variations during the ESC cycle. The cycle begins under low idle conditions and evolves through different operating stages combining load percentages and normalized engine speeds. Engine operating conditions are defined by the standard using rotational regimes A, B and C, calculated according to: Rotation A = $n_{lo} + 25\%(n_{hi} - n_{lo})$; Rotation B = $n_{lo} + 50\%(n_{hi} - n_{lo})$; Rotation C = $n_{lo} + 75\%(n_{hi} - n_{lo})$

Figures 2(a) and 2(b) present the performance curves obtained for the Mercedes-Benz Accelo and Ford Cargo vehicles operating with B0 fuel. The Ford Cargo vehicle complies with the PROCONVE P5 emission standard, while the Mercedes-Benz Accelo complies with the PROCONVE P7 standard. Additionally, the evaluated vehicles present an approximately eleven-year difference between manufacturing dates, representing distinct technological generations of the Brazilian heavy-duty fleet.

Figure 1. (a) MB Accelo using B0 as fuel. Figure 2(b) Ford Cargo using B0 as fuel.

Source: Authors (2026).

The experimental results demonstrated that the older Ford Cargo vehicle exhibited greater sensitivity to biodiesel concentration variations. Approximately 10% variation was observed between the highest and lowest power values obtained during the tests. Operating with B7 fuel, the vehicle reached approximately 107.5 hp at 2100 rpm, whereas operation with B20 resulted in power values close to 96.8 hp at the same engine speed range.

For the Mercedes-Benz Accelo vehicle, no significant variation in maximum power output was observed with increasing biodiesel concentration. This behavior indicates improved combustion management and compensation capability associated with the more advanced electronic injection and engine control systems adopted in the newer vehicle technology.

A similar trend was observed in the torque analysis. The Ford Cargo vehicle presented greater torque variation as biodiesel concentration increased. Approximately 5% variation was observed between B7 and B20 operation at 2000 rpm. In addition, operation with B7 fuel resulted in greater engine elasticity, maintaining higher torque levels throughout the evaluated operating range. The maximum torque obtained with B7 was approximately 6% higher than that obtained with B20 and 3.5% higher than that observed with B15 under the maximum torque operating condition.

The Mercedes-Benz Accelo vehicle also presented small torque variations relative to B7 operation. Under this condition, the maximum torque peak reached approximately 51.5 kgfm at 1000 rpm, representing a difference close to 6% compared with B20 at the same engine speed. However, the torque peaks presented discontinuities associated with gear shifting events during the experimental procedure. After approximately 1500 rpm, the torque behavior remained relatively stable until the end of the test.

The reduced torque and power sensitivity observed in the Mercedes-Benz Accelo vehicle indicates that the advanced electronic injection and combustion management systems were capable of compensating for changes in biodiesel concentration during engine operation. In contrast, the older Ford Cargo technology showed greater performance degradation under higher biodiesel blends, suggesting increased sensitivity of older combustion systems to variations in fuel physicochemical properties.

3.2 ETC Cycle Emission Results

The presented results correspond to the compilation of 1800 transient operating points with 1 s resolution obtained during the ETC cycle tests performed for each evaluated vehicle. The emission limits adopted in this study follow the requirements established for PROCONVE P5 (Ford Cargo) and PROCONVE P7 (Mercedes-Benz Accelo) standards. Table 5 summarizes the maximum emission limits established for the ETC cycle according to the corresponding PROCONVE phases.

Table 5. Emission limits to ETC Cycles for different Proconve phases.

Proconve Phase	CO (g/kWh)	HC (g/kWh)	NO _x (g/kWh)
P5 (Ford Cargo)	4.0	0.55	3.5
P7 (MB Accelo)	4.0	NA	2.0

Source: CONAMA n° 315/2002 e CONAMA n° 403/2008.

The experimental results demonstrated that both evaluated vehicles complied with the emission limits established for carbon monoxide (CO), hydrocarbons (HC) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). For both vehicles, the measured CO emissions remained significantly below the regulatory limits during all evaluated operating conditions. Hydrocarbon emissions were also very low and can be considered residual within the exhaust gas flow. Table 6 presents the specific emissions and brake specific fuel consumption (bsfc) obtained during the ETC cycle for all evaluated biodiesel blends.

Table 6. Specific emissions - ETC Cycle

Ford Cargo Fuel	bsfc (kg/kWh)	NO _x (g/kWh)	CO (g/kWh)	HC (g/kWh)	CO ₂ (g/kWh)
BO	0.17	1.80	0.58	0.016	228.7
B7	0.22	1.80	0.59	0.016	228.8
B15	0.24	1.95	0.61	0.012	249.4
B20	0.23	1.99	0.59	0.013	243.4
B70	0.25	1.99	0.59	0.014	237.1
MB ACCELO Fuel	bsfc (kg/kWh)	NO _x (g/kWh)	CO (g/kWh)	HC (g/kWh)	CO ₂ (g/kWh)
BO	0.16	1.65	0.67	0.010	190.5
B7	0.19	1.60	0.69	0.008	192.3
B15	0.23	1.61	0.94	0.016	197.8

Ford Cargo						
Fuel	bsfc (kg/kWh)	NO _x (g/kWh)	CO (g/kWh)	HC (g/kWh)	CO ₂ (g/kWh)	
BO	0.17	1.80	0.58	0.016	228.7	
B7	0.22	1.80	0.59	0.016	228.8	
B15	0.24	1.95	0.61	0.012	249.4	
B20	0.23	1.99	0.59	0.013	243.4	
B70	0.25	1.99	0.59	0.014	237.1	
MB ACCELO						
Fuel	bsfc (kg/kWh)	NO _x (g/kWh)	CO (g/kWh)	HC (g/kWh)	CO ₂ (g/kWh)	
B20	0.21	1.60	1.12	0.057	191.7	
B70	0.26	1.80	0.77	0.005	203.4	

Source: Authors (2026).

Nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions were strongly influenced by vehicle technology and biodiesel concentration. For the Ford Cargo vehicle, a progressive increase in NO_x emissions was observed with increasing biodiesel content. The highest NO_x emissions were obtained for B20 and B70 operation, corresponding to an increase of approximately 9.6% compared with B7 operation. This behavior is associated with the higher oxygen content of biodiesel fuels, which may promote higher local combustion temperatures and intensify thermal NO_x formation mechanisms.

In contrast, the Mercedes-Benz Accelo vehicle exhibited relatively stable NO_x emissions throughout the evaluated biodiesel blends. Variations remained close to 1% between B7 and B20 operation, demonstrating the effectiveness of the SCR aftertreatment system combined with advanced electronic injection control strategies. Only under B70 operation was a more pronounced increase in NO_x emissions observed.

Regarding fuel consumption, both vehicles presented higher bsfc values as biodiesel concentration increased. For the Ford Cargo vehicle, the least favorable operating condition occurred with B15 fuel, resulting in approximately 6.7% higher fuel consumption compared with B7 operation. The Mercedes-Benz Accelo vehicle also exhibited increased bsfc values with higher biodiesel blends, reaching approximately 19% variation between B7 and B15 operations.

Carbon monoxide emissions remained low for both vehicles under all evaluated conditions, indicating satisfactory combustion efficiency during the ETC cycle. Hydrocarbon emissions also remained at residual levels, particularly for the Ford Cargo vehicle. The higher HC value observed for the Mercedes-Benz Accelo under B20 operation may be associated with transient combustion instability during specific operating phases of the ETC cycle.

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions showed greater stability for the Mercedes-Benz Accelo vehicle, whereas the Ford Cargo exhibited larger variations with biodiesel concentration. These

differences indicate that newer combustion and after-treatment technologies are better capable of compensating for variations in biodiesel physicochemical properties during transient operation.

3.3 ESC Cycle Emission Results

The ESC cycle was designed to subject the engine to a sequence of stationery operating conditions under high load, allowing the extraction of maximum engine power and the evaluation of pollutant emissions under severe operating regimes. During the test procedure, the engine operates at different combinations of load and rotational speed conditions, which are subsequently used to quantify specific emissions according to ABNT NBR 15634 procedures. Table 7 presents the emission limits established for the ESC cycle according to the corresponding PROCONVE phases.

Table 7. ESC limits for different Proconve phases

Proconve Phase	CO (g/kWh)	HC (g/kWh)	NO _x (g/kWh)
P5 (Ford Cargo)	2.1	0.66	5.0
P7 (MB Accelo)	1.5	0.46	2.0

Source: Authors (2026).

During the ESC cycle, the engine operates under elevated load conditions, allowing a more evident assessment of the effects of biodiesel concentration on combustion behavior and atmospheric emissions. Under these operating conditions, the influence of combustion efficiency and exhaust aftertreatment technologies becomes more evident, particularly regarding NO_x and CO₂ emissions. Tables 8 and 9 present the specific emissions and brake specific fuel consumption (bsfc) obtained for the Ford Cargo and Mercedes-Benz Accelo vehicles during the ESC cycle.

Table 8. Ford Cargo – Cycle ESC

Fuel	bsfc (kg/kWh)	NO _x (g/kWh)	CO (g/kWh)	HC (g/kWh)	CO ₂ (g/kWh)
B0	0.19	3.46	0.43	0.011	466.3
B7	0.20	3.73	0.91	0.007	463.4
B15	0.23	3.67	0.89	0.003	482.7
B20	0.28	4.19	3.48	0.002	652.5
B70	0.34	4.88	3.89	0.006	701.8

Table 9. MB Accelo – Ciclo ESC

Fuel	bsfc (kg/kWh)	NO _x (g/kWh)	CO (g/kWh)	HC (g/kWh)	CO ₂ (g/kWh)
B0	0.23	1.83	0.48	0.002	161.7
B7	0.24	1.90	0.64	0.005	171.0
B15	0.27	1.53	0.84	0.002	120.3
B20	0.27	1.91	2.83	0.008	172.0

Fuel	bsfc (kg/kWh)	NO_x (g/kWh)	CO (g/kWh)	HC (g/kWh)	CO₂ (g/kWh)
B70	0.37	2.53	3.89	0.016	125.3

Source: Authors (2026).

The experimental results demonstrated that both evaluated vehicles complied with the current emission regulations for their respective PROCONVE phases. However, significant differences were observed between the two vehicle technologies regarding pollutant formation and fuel consumption behavior under high engine load conditions.

Nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions remained below the regulatory limits for both vehicles during all evaluated operating conditions. Nevertheless, the Ford Cargo vehicle exhibited a progressive increase in NO_x emissions with increasing biodiesel concentration, reaching 4.88 g/kWh under B70 operation. This behavior is associated with higher combustion temperatures promoted by the oxygenated nature of biodiesel fuels under elevated load conditions. The Mercedes-Benz Accelo vehicle exhibited significantly lower NO_x emissions throughout the ESC cycle due to the combined action of the Diesel Particulate Filter (DPF), Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR) and Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR) systems. The SCR system, operating with the injection of a urea-water solution (ARLA-32), effectively reduced NO_x emissions under high-load operation.

Regarding fuel consumption, both vehicles showed increased bsfc values as biodiesel concentration increased. However, the Ford Cargo vehicle exhibited greater sensitivity to biodiesel blending, particularly for B20 and B70 operations. This behavior indicates lower combustion adaptation capability in the older engine technology when operating with high biodiesel concentrations.

Carbon monoxide (CO) emissions also increased under higher biodiesel concentrations during the ESC cycle, especially for B20 and B70 operations. This increase may be associated with localized combustion instability and reduced combustion efficiency under elevated load conditions. Hydrocarbon (HC) emissions remained very low for both vehicles during the ESC cycle, indicating satisfactory combustion efficiency under stationary operating conditions.

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions exhibited distinct behavior between the evaluated vehicles. During the ETC cycle, CO₂ emissions remained relatively stable due to the predominance of low-load and idle operating conditions throughout the transient cycle. In contrast, the ESC cycle produced significantly higher CO₂ emission levels due to the elevated engine load conditions imposed during the test. The Ford Cargo vehicle exhibited substantially higher CO₂ emissions than the Mercedes-Benz Accelo vehicle under all evaluated fuel blends.

A direct relationship between biodiesel concentration, reduced engine power output and increased specific CO₂ emissions was also observed.

For example, when operating with B20 fuel, the Ford Cargo vehicle delivered approximately 96.8 hp accompanied by average CO₂ emissions close to 652.5 g/kWh. Under B7 operation, the same vehicle reached approximately 107.5 hp with CO₂ emissions around 463.4 g/kWh, corresponding to an approximate 29% reduction in specific CO₂ emissions.

These results indicate that newer diesel technologies equipped with advanced combustion control and exhaust aftertreatment systems exhibit greater stability and lower environmental sensitivity under biodiesel operation, particularly under severe engine load conditions.

4. Conclusion

The experimental tests conducted according to ABNT NBR 15634 allowed the evaluation of emissions, fuel consumption and performance behavior of two heavy-duty diesel vehicles operating with different biodiesel blends under ETC and ESC driving cycles.

The results demonstrated that increasing biodiesel concentration affected older and newer vehicle technologies differently. In the ETC cycle, both vehicles exhibited gradual increases in pollutant emissions as biodiesel content increased. Carbon monoxide (CO) emissions remained relatively stable for Ford Cargo, whereas the Mercedes-Benz Accelo showed greater sensitivity to biodiesel concentration, with approximately 39% variation between B7 and B20. Hydrocarbon (HC) emissions remained at residual levels for all evaluated fuel blends and well below the regulatory limits established for the corresponding PROCONVE phases.

Significant differences were observed regarding nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions. The Mercedes-Benz Accelo, equipped with EGR, DPF and SCR aftertreatment systems using ARLA-32 injection, exhibited substantially lower NO_x emissions than the older Ford Cargo vehicle. The SCR system demonstrated high effectiveness in controlling NO_x formation during biodiesel operation, particularly under transient conditions. In contrast, the Ford Cargo vehicle showed progressive NO_x increases with higher biodiesel concentrations due to the absence of advanced aftertreatment technologies.

The ESC cycle, conducted under full-load operating conditions, intensified the differences between the evaluated technologies. Under B20 operation, both vehicles exhibited elevated CO emissions, exceeding the certification limits established for their respective PROCONVE phases. The causes of these anomalies could not be conclusively identified and require further investigation. Nevertheless, HC emissions remained low throughout the ESC cycle for both vehicles.

Performance and fuel consumption analyses demonstrated that the Ford Cargo vehicle was more sensitive to biodiesel concentration increases. Operation with B7 resulted in the highest torque and power values combined with the lowest specific fuel consumption, whereas B20 operation produced lower performance and approximately 27% higher fuel consumption. In contrast, the Mercedes-Benz Accelo maintained relatively stable torque and power output regardless of biodiesel concentration, although specific fuel consumption increased by approximately 11.6% between B7 and B15 operations.

The results indicate that older diesel technologies are more susceptible to performance degradation and emission increases under higher biodiesel blends, mainly due to limitations in combustion control and fuel injection management systems. Conversely, newer vehicles equipped with advanced electronic management and exhaust aftertreatment technologies demonstrated greater operational stability and improved emission control capability.

Considering the aging profile of the Brazilian heavy-duty fleet, the findings of this study suggest that increasing biodiesel blending mandates may affect older vehicles more significantly than newer technologies. This aspect becomes particularly relevant considering recent Brazilian policies proposing biodiesel blends up to B25. In addition to environmental impacts, higher biodiesel concentrations may also influence maintenance intervals, operational costs and fleet durability, especially for vehicles not originally designed for elevated biodiesel operation.

Therefore, future studies should investigate the long-term effects of high biodiesel concentrations on engine durability, maintenance requirements and real-world emissions in aging heavy-duty fleets operating under Brazilian conditions.

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